

COMFORTage

Prediction, monitoring and personalized recommendations
for prevention and relief of dementia and frailty

*The ETHAI Methodology
A Context-Sensitive, Actionable
Approach to Ethics of AI in
Healthcare*

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What is this about?

A methodology for Ethics-by-design, developed within a project on AI based healthcare in Dementia and Frailty: EU funded COMFORTage project

- **Why this methodology?**
- **Theoretical foundation**
- **Components and how it works**

COMFORTage Project Context

- **Focus:** Dementia and frailty care AI based systems (diagnostic and assistive)
- **Challenge:** Vulnerable populations requiring specialized ethical considerations
- **Goal:** Operationalize ethics throughout the whole R&I process but particularly the AI development lifecycle

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Where AI Ethics Frameworks Fall Short

Gap between principles and implementation: Most frameworks remain abstract

Missing relational context: healthcare AI must account for the full socio-technical system

One-size-fits-all limitations: Healthcare AI needs domain-specific considerations

Post-hoc vs. by-design: Ethics as afterthought vs. integrated from inception

ETHAI principles

Context-Sensitivity

Domain-specific adaptation
of general ethics guidelines

Healthcare-specific
requirements derivation

Stakeholder-driven
contextual relevance

Actionability

Translation from abstract
principles to implementable
specifications

Concrete technical requirements
with measurable criteria

Direct integration into
development workflows

Multi-disciplinarity

Shared vocabulary
development between
ethics and technical teams

Bidirectional feedback
mechanisms

Iterativity

Continuous refinement
cycles

Adaptive requirements
based on implementation
feedback

Evolutionary approach to
ethics compliance

Theoretical Foundation

12 Ethics Requirements

Image from Volpini et al. (2025). The ETHAI Methodology. In: Papaleonidas et al (eds) Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations. AIAI 2025 IFIP WG 12.5 International Workshops. AIAI 2025. IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology, vol 754. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-97313-0_19

Phase 1: Ethics Requirements Identification

Technical Activities:

- AI system inventory and mapping
- Stakeholder risk assessment sessions
- Case-based ethics reasoning workshops
- Requirement prioritization matrix

Output:

- High-level ethics requirements catalog
- Risk assessment documentation
- Stakeholder concern registry

Phase 2: Requirement Translation

Technical Activities:

- Interdisciplinary co-design sessions
- Abstract-to-concrete requirement mapping

Output:

- Technical specification development
- Measurability criteria definition

Phase 3: Implementation and Refinement

Technical Activities:

- Iterative development with ethics team collaboration
- Performance vs. ethics trade-off analysis
- Continuous integration of ethics requirements
- Technical constraint accommodation

Phase 4: Assessment and Evaluation

Technical Activities:

- Ethics compliance testing
- User feedback integration systems
- Expert review protocols
- Impact assessment metrics

Output:

- Assessment / Evaluation
- Requirements refinement

Key implementation challenges and solutions

Performance vs. Ethics Trade-offs

- **Challenge:** e.g. Transparency mechanisms creating latency
- **Solution:** Collaborative reassessment and balanced implementation

Requirement Specification Precision

- **Challenge:** Translating qualitative ethics into quantitative metrics
- **Solution:** Iterative refinement with measurable acceptance criteria

Cross-disciplinary Communication

- **Challenge:** Technical and ethics vocabulary alignment
- **Solution:** Structured co-design sessions and shared documentation

Stakeholder Engagement Complexity

- **Challenge:** Diverse perspectives integration
- **Solution:** Semi-structured risk assessment and prioritization frameworks

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Key Takeaways

- **Ethics as Technical Requirement:** Treat ethical considerations as concrete, implementable specifications
- **Early Integration:** Embed ethics requirements from system architecture phase
- **Collaborative Development:** Establish structured communication with ethics experts
- **Measurable Compliance:** Define quantitative metrics for ethical performance
- **Iterative Refinement:** Plan for continuous ethics-technical co-evolution

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